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THE ROLE OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN ENSURING EMPLOYMENT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL

Abstract: The article is devoted to a comprehensive analysis of the role of human capital as a key factor in ensuring sustainable employment at the regional level in the context of digitalization and structural transformation of the economy. The theoretical and methodological foundations of the concept of human capital, its evolution in the works of leading researchers (T. Schulz, G. Becker, J. Sachs, etc.) and the importance of qualitative characteristics of the workforce for the modern labor market are considered. The work emphasizes that cognitive, digital and interpersonal skills come to the forefront in importance, ensuring the flexibility and adaptability of employed persons to the challenges of the knowledge economy, "green" and digital sectors. A classification of regions of Uzbekistan by the level of human capital development is proposed, disparities affecting the employment structure are identified. Particular attention is paid to the development of targeted measures depending on the industry, demographic and digital specifics of the territories.

Key words: human capital, regional employment, digitalization, professional training, institutional support, sustainable development, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Maqola iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va tarkibiy o'zgartirishlar sharoitida mintaqaviy darajada barqaror bandlikni ta'minlashning asosiy omili sifatida inson kapitalining rolini har tomonlama tahlil qilishga bag'ishlangan. Inson kapitali kontseptsiyasining nazariy va uslubiy asoslari, uning yetakchi tadqiqotchilar (T.Shuls, G.Bekker, J. Saks va boshqalar) ishlarida evolyutsiyasi va zamonaviy mehnat bozori uchun ishchi kuchining sifat xususiyatlarining ahamiyati ko'rib chiqiladi. Ishda ta'kidlanishicha, kognitiv, raqamli va shaxslararo ko'nikmalar birinchi o'rinda turadi, bu ish bilan band shaxslarning bilim iqtisodiyoti, "yashil" va raqamli sektorlar muammolariga moslashuvchanligi va moslashishini ta'minlaydi. O'zbekiston hududlarini inson kapitali rivojlanish darajasi bo'yicha tasniflash taklif etilmoqda, bandlik tarkibiga ta'sir etuvchi nomutanosibliklar aniqlangan. Hududlarning tarmoq, demografik va raqamli o'ziga xos xususiyatlaridan kelib chiqib, maqsadli chora-tadbirlar ishlab chiqishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: inson kapitali, mintaqaviy bandlik, raqamlashtirish, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, institutsional qo'llab-quvvatlash, barqaror rivojlanish, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена комплексному анализу роли человеческого капитала как ключевого фактора обеспечения устойчивой занятости на региональном уровне в условиях цифровизации и структурной трансформации экономики. Рассматриваются теоретико-методологические основы концепции человеческого капитала, её эволюция в трудах ведущих исследователей (Т. Шульц, Г. Беккер, Дж. Сакс и др.), а также значение качественных характеристик рабочей силы для современного рынка труда. В работе подчёркивается, что на первый план по значимости выходят когнитивные, цифровые и межличностные навыки, обеспечивающие гибкость и адаптивность занятых к вызовам экономики знаний, «зелёного» и цифрового секторов. Предложена

классификация регионов Узбекистана по уровню развития человеческого капитала, выявлены диспропорции, влияющие на структуру занятости. Особое внимание уделено разработке целевых мер в зависимости от отраслевой, демографической и цифровой специфики территорий.

Ключевые слова: человеческий капитал, региональная занятость, цифровизация, профессиональная подготовка кадров, институциональная поддержка, устойчивое развитие, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of rapid digital, demographic and technological transformations, human capital is acquiring key importance as the foundation for sustainable socio-economic development of regions. It forms not only the qualitative characteristics of the workforce, but also determines the ability of the economy to adapt to changing conditions of the global and local labor markets. Modern challenges - automation of production, changes in the structure of demand for labor, deepening regional disparities - exacerbate the need to rethink the role of human capital in the formation of effective employment.

At the regional level, human capital is not only a social asset, but also a strategic resource that determines the economic competitiveness of a territory. Regions with developed education systems, professional training, and medical infrastructure demonstrate higher employment, resilience to economic shocks, and the ability to generate jobs in high-value-added industries.

In this context, the formation of a flexible and adaptive system of regional employment based on investments in human capital is particularly relevant. The development of such systems requires taking into account the characteristics of the regional economy, demographic structure, level of digitalization and availability of social services.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Theoretical foundations of the concept of “human capital”. In modern conditions, human capital is becoming a determining factor in the formation of sustainable and high-quality employment at the regional level. It is a set of knowledge, skills, professional competencies, health and social experience that determine the economic activity of an individual. The development of human capital helps to increase the adaptability of labor resources, their ability to master new technologies, work in the conditions of digitalization and environmental transformation of the economy. It is highly qualified personnel that become the basis of a flexible labor market capable of quickly responding to structural changes.

The concept of human capital was introduced by T. Schultz and developed in the works of G. Becker, who considered investments in education and health as a form of accumulation of capital that generates income [1]. In a broader sense, human capital covers the knowledge, skills, competencies, health and innovative behavior of an individual, which form his labor and economic potential.

According to T. Schultz, “education increases productivity, allows for more flexible adaptation to changes in technology and economic structure, and, consequently, reduces the risks of unemployment” [2]. J. Sachs emphasizes that high quality human capital is the key to overcoming poverty and creating jobs, especially in regions with limited resources [3].

According to the authors, the ability to learn and adapt is becoming more important than knowledge of a specific profession, making flexibility and lifelong learning skills central to employment [4]. The OECD argues that regions with higher levels of human capital development experience lower unemployment and are better able to adapt to economic change [5].

According to Bloom and Canning, population health and longevity form the basis for long-term employment, since workers in good health remain in economically active age longer and increase overall productivity [6]. Heckman emphasizes that early investments in human capital – especially in education and skills – yield the greatest socio-economic benefits and sustainable employment levels in the future [7].

Some authors note that it is not just the years of education, but the quality of education and the development of cognitive skills that determine employment success and productivity growth at the regional level [8]. According to the ILO, the development of human capital through training, occupational safety and health, and preparation for market changes contributes not only to reducing unemployment, but also to the creation of “sustainable” jobs [9].

According to a World Bank report, human capital is an asset that directly affects the competitiveness of countries and regions, and low levels of education and skills limit the population’s participation in the economy [10].

The impact of human capital on employment is manifested in both quantitative and qualitative aspects, but its role in the modern economy goes far beyond the traditional idea of the connection between education and employment. Today, we are witnessing a systemic transformation of employment: new forms of labor are being formed, requirements for skills are changing, and the importance of flexibility and adaptability of workers is increasing. In these conditions, human capital is becoming not just a factor of competitiveness, but a condition for social sustainability.

In our opinion, it is the qualitative characteristics of human capital – cognitive abilities, level of digital literacy, ability to learn and interact interpersonally – that form the basis of the new employment structure. The employee ceases to be only a bearer of a specific profession – he becomes a participant in a dynamic system, in which not so much his static set of knowledge is valued, but rather the ability to quickly master new roles and tasks. This is especially relevant at the regional level, where the gap in the level of human capital causes employment asymmetry.

Statistical data and analytical reviews of the ILO, the World Bank and the OECD confirm that regions with a developed education and training system demonstrate higher employment rates, a smaller share of the informal sector and greater resilience to crises. We believe it is necessary to take these patterns into account in national and regional employment policies. In this case, the emphasis should be placed not on quantitative indicators (for example, the number of graduates), but on the formation of meaningful, multi-level human potential.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Four key areas of influence of human capital on employment can be identified:

Increased employability – higher levels of education and qualifications increase the chances of employment, especially in a competitive market environment;

Increased productivity – quality skills enable you to perform more complex tasks and create greater added value;

Reducing structural unemployment – the ability to retrain and adapt reduces the time it takes to find a new job in the context of economic transformation;

Development of new segments of the labor market – human capital is the driver of the emergence of creative, digital and “green” professions.

Thus, investments in human capital development are not just a social obligation of the state, but an economically justified strategy aimed at forming a flexible and adaptive labor market. It is especially important to develop these processes at the regional level, based on the industry and demographic specifics of the territories.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The role of human capital in regional employment policy is acquiring strategic importance in the context of global transformations and growing regional imbalances. Human capital is a key resource that contributes not only to the growth of labor productivity, but also to the formation of a new employment structure focused on innovative, digital and «green» industries. In the context of increasing competition for qualified personnel between regions, the ability of a territory to form and retain human capital is becoming an important condition for sustainable socio-economic development.

A special role in such a policy is played by mechanisms of continuous education, professional retraining and advanced training. In the context of technological shifts and automation of traditional industries, the ability of the population to adapt to new labor market requirements directly depends on the flexibility of the education system and its connection with the regional economy. Therefore, an effective regional policy should provide for interaction between educational institutions, businesses and government bodies to coordinate the needs of the labor market with the supply of qualified specialists.

Thus, human capital is not only a factor in ensuring the current level of employment, but also the basis for the long-term sustainability of regional development. However, the efficiency of using this resource varies significantly between regions, which requires a differentiated approach to the formation of regional policy.

In order to more accurately classify territories and determine priorities in resource distribution, the author’s classification of regions of Uzbekistan by the level of human capital development is proposed (Table 1). The classification is based on a generalized assessment of education coverage, digital accessibility, development of the vocational training system and the availability of basic social infrastructure.

At the same time, rural and remote regions such as Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions are characterized by a relatively low share of employment in the formal sector and limited human resources in higher education. This indicates a shortage of human capital, which exacerbates the problem of hidden unemployment and hinders the development of modern segments of the economy.

The gap between regions with high (Tashkent, Samarkand region) and low (Sirdarya, Navoiy regions) concentration of academic personnel is noteworthy. This imbalance indicates the need for targeted measures to develop educational infrastructure and stimulate training of personnel in regions with low levels of human capital. Thus, the data in the table confirm that the level of human capital development directly correlates with the sustainability of regional employment and economic diversification.

Thus, for regions with a high level of capital, measures to stimulate high-tech and creative employment are relevant, while for territories with a low level, basic education, digital literacy and access to retraining systems are of primary importance. Such a typology can become the basis for developing targeted programs aimed at the sustainable development of regions, taking into account their socio-economic specifics.

Thus, human capital is not only a factor in ensuring the current level of employment, but also the basis for long-term sustainability of regional development. By investing in human capital - education, health, innovative competencies – the region creates the prerequisites for attracting investment, developing small and medium-sized businesses, increasing export potential and improving the quality of life of the population. In this regard, the development of human capital should be included among the priorities of the regional employment strategy, as a necessary condition for increasing competitiveness and social stability.

Differences in human capital levels between regions generate inequality in employment. Thus, regions with a high level of education and developed infrastructure create more jobs in high-tech sectors, while agricultural regions often face low qualifications and high hidden unemployment. According to the World Bank, an increase in the level of education by 1 year increases the chances of employment by 7-10% in developing countries [11].

Institutional support for human capital development is a fundamental element of effective human capital formation at the regional level. In the context of the transition to a knowledge economy and growing instability of the labor market, institutions are becoming not just a backdrop for the implementation of educational and social programs, but active agents of employment transformation. Their task is to create a sustainable ecosystem of interaction between the state, educational institutions, business and civil society.

The formation and development of human capital is impossible without systemic institutional support. It is institutions – government agencies, educational organizations, research centers and business structures – that create conditions for people's knowledge, skills and competencies to become a resource for social and economic development.

Such support includes not only funding for education and healthcare, but also the development of a regulatory framework, strategic documents, professional training programs, certification mechanisms, and qualification assessment. The role of institutions is to establish the “rules of the game” in the labor market – from the content of educational programs to the conditions for access to retraining and advanced training.

Institutional support plays a key role in the formation and development of human capital, as it covers a wide range of areas, from strategic planning to the direct implementation of professional training programs. Below is a table reflecting the main areas of institutional influence and a brief description of each of them.

Table 3. Institutional support for human capital development*

Direction of support	Description
State strategies and programs	Development and implementation of national strategies in the field of education and employment
Reforms of the education and training system	Updating the content and structure of education in accordance with the requirements of the labor market
National qualification and certification systems	Creation of qualification frameworks, recognition and assessment of competencies
Support for R&D and digital competencies	Investments in the development of science, innovation and digital skills
Programs vocational training and retraining	Organization of courses, trainings, retraining centers

* Compiled by the author

Modern challenges of digitalization and the “green” economy caused by accelerated digitalization and the environmental shift in economic policy make qualitatively new demands on human capital. The change in

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